

Language	Type of item	Name - for retrieval tools only write e.g. "DaMSym Latin"	Short description (what it does) - not necessary for Retrieval tools	Link to Source Material / repository	Link to Operative Web Tool (if present)	Screenshot from the figma marketplace of the current status or image o altro of the tool	Future short and/or long term development prospects	Additional Information
Sanskrit	Software (e.g. lemmatizer)	Sanskrit Word Search Engine	Specialized word search engine developed for exploring Sanskrit corpora, published as Sourcecode	https://github.com/IrfanAliBabar		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1u84TqrNz98Ngx_KWk56ObFp8ePSELPlE , https://drive.google.com/open?id=1YLc4SYHozsXMUQRZKLVwgdSOKkQmSGwA		
Sanskrit	Software (e.g. lemmatizer)	SandhiSplitter	Attention-Based Bi-Encoder model to predict valid split locations in Sanskrit compound words	https://github.com/IrfanAliBabar		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1S2XH_Lgv3Se2DHit1ox172XtSD4K2wGw		
Sanskrit	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Sanskrit		http://barracuda.isti.cnr.it:40010/	Tool in fase di pubblicazione	https://drive.google.com/open?id=17acV5QTVq7EsVwLldkOiqvH4QQJY9bHf , https://drive.google.com/open?id=11g7j_r-eIDvFTZqFmpaWAu5gsGD4Qs79 , https://drive.google.com/open?id=11izRTR07RWI073uUCMC7A7n4NBK5oLVV	Implementation in search fields, allowing users to search by period, distinguishing between Vedic and post-Vedic texts.	
Arabic	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Arabic		https://kitab-project.org/metadata/		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1RQf14Fxe10zP-AhXrikQ_dgc95TiDbzk		
Latin	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Latin		https://hadith2text.aimh.cloud.isti.cnr.it/		https://drive.google.com/open?id=13SCARKa5YaFtqxd8_9ZBQT0ACKtCSE		
Ancient Greek	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Greek		https://hadith2text.aimh.cloud.isti.cnr.it/		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1zqjNoSX5B79jUHEN7LCXHZf8uxWmRKMi		
Cross - Latin and Ancient Greek	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Cross Latin and Greek		https://hadith2text.aimh.cloud.isti.cnr.it/		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1AYe_eVFrj0uSQ62jYowL-NZGp3Hu7qMg		
German	Linguistic Model (es. SPhiBERTa)	GerBERTa	SPhiBERTa fintuned for German with SimCSE	https://zenodo.org/records/17432492				
Church Slavonic	Software (e.g. lemmatizer)	Lemmatizer – Old Church Slavonic	A GUI-based lemmatization tool for Old Church Slavonic that uses a dictionary of word–lemma pairs to map inflected forms to their canonical lemmas. It supports text input, interactive lemmatization, dataset exploration, and word–lemma table visualization. The system achieves good accuracy on OCS texts and can be adapted for other ancient languages with similar resources.	https://github.com/usmannawaz01/Old-Church-Slavonic-Lemmatizer		https://drive.google.com/open?id=1e1c-0vl87ebMnxllF2nHMiv1MigtVVxe		For Church Slavonic, as well as for other languages, the Stanza tool (https://stanfordnlp.github.io/stanza/) works very well, but it does not recognize the older South Slavic texts, such as the Serbian/Bulgarian redactions, and often there are phonetic variations that are not detected by the lemmatizer and are not even lexicalized in Gorazd, one of the most commonly used online dictionaries for Church Slavonic. Therefore, we are trying to create a tool that can also handle these texts. Another goal for the near future is to make the tool available on the marketplace.
Church Slavonic	Software (e.g. lemmatizer)	PUA Handling System for the Conversion of Text Corpora in Old Church Slavonic	By implementing a dictionary-based Unicode mapping, we enabled systematic conversion of non-standard PUA characters into canonical Unicode code points, improving the reliability of text processing. Tailored for Old Church Slavonic, these mappings enhance the readability and accurate representation of texts in digital repositories (e.g.: the Cyrillicmethodiana web portal - https://histdict.unisofia.bg/), the main source for WP4's semantic retrieval tool. Consistent aggregated visualisation—central to the tool—requires integrating font usage with explicit PUA-to-Unicode correspondence tables. This framework not only resolves current technical issues but also provides a solid foundation for future linguistic, historical, and cultural analyses.	https://github.com/usmannawaz01/OCS-Text-Processing ; https://github.com/usmannawaz01/OCS-Text-Processing ; https://na01.safelinks.protection.outlook.com/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fdrive.google.com%2Ffile%2F%2F1J-5xwmN3oaibnKky4BJvllN7HOLsvHxX%2Fview%3Fusp%3Dsharing&data=05%7C02%7C%7C4059448f8f3648bcdad808de312aca84%7C84df9e7fe9f640afb435aaaaaaaaaaaa%7C1%7C0%7C639002260167492861%7CUknown%7CTWFpbGZsb3d8eyJFbXB0eU1hcGkiOnRydWUsIlYiOiIwLjAuMDAwMCIsIlAiOiJXaW4zMilSkFOljoITWFpbClldUljoyfQ%3D%3D%7C0%7C%7C%7C&sdata=gsYdmzB3msgGX3EkhnGfMki7WBcDLqznsikyztOyOA%3D&reserved=0	The link to Operative web tool is currently unavailable, and it remains uncertain whether the development of the tool can be carried out during the final phase of the project.	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1BHRIA5myMvOPTbup278PB4TKLT8j0iP9 , https://drive.google.com/open?id=1RolsrgcZ1dVvvdEG0r_ikQkKR9_5vuvq	We are currently working on the integration of additional manually developed correspondence maps between PUA characters and Unicode code points. In addition to the character map derived from the Azbuka Very (Православный портал Азбука Веры - Orthodox Portal ABC of Faith - https://azbyka.ru/bogoslužhenie/cu/kanon-svyatoj-i-zhivonachalnoj-troicze/) digital library, we have created a mapping for texts available on the manuscript.ru digital library (Манускрипт - Slavonic Written Heritage- http://manuscripts.ru/mns/main?p_text=44342283), as some texts—subject to partial copyright—were included through the collaboration established with Prof. Victor Baranov, curator of the corpus. This map is still under review. At present, we are developing a map for texts available on the Pravmir.com digital library (Orthodox Christianity and the World – The Daily Website on How to be an Orthodox Christian Today, https://www.pravmir.ru/). We will continue to integrate additional maps until the end of the project.	In the future, it is also likely that work will be undertaken to develop the tool for potential inclusion on the marketplace of the ITSERR project.

Church Slavonic	Dataset (es. corpus)	DIACU: A dataset for the DIACHronic analysis of Church Slavonic	<p>We have developed a large-scale dataset of texts in the Church Slavonic language, enriched with chronological and geographic annotations. The dataset comprises a total of 652 documents representing four distinct language variants. This collection can serve as a unified corpus for linguists and scholars in the humanities to conduct detailed investigations of diachronic language phenomena. Additionally, it can function as a training resource for machine-learning-based methodologies aimed at text attribution. The development of the DIACU dataset addresses the specific challenges associated with Old Church Slavonic, a historical language characterized by the limited digitization of texts and, in cases where digital collections exist, the dispersion of these resources across multiple digital libraries and portals. The DIACU dataset integrates five primary collections of texts: Cyrillo-Methodiana (accessible via uni-sofia.bg), Syntacticus (syntacticus.org), Old Russian Hagiographic Literature (spbu.ru), a selection from the National Corpus of the Russian Language (RNC) (ruscorpora.ru), and a sample from the Ruthenian Corpus: UD_Old_East_Slavic_Ruthenian. By bringing these resources together into a single, cohesive dataset, DIACU provides a comprehensive foundation for both qualitative and computational study of the history and development of Slavic languages.</p>	https://github.com/MariaCassese/DIACU	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1-TfhirTmXMYztFyhNwmwgiBLCV1EB9LX	<p>In the future, we aim to extend this dataset by incorporating additional texts available from online libraries, provided they are in formats consistent with those already included in DIACU, and where collaboration with the respective curators can be established. Further opportunities for expansion arise from contacts already developed during the course of this project; for instance, we consider the PRIN project entitled Humanistic Italy and Sixteenth-Century Muscovy in Dialogue: Digitization and Digital Mapping of the Work of Maximus the Greek (Universities of Pisa, Univeristy of Chieti-Pescara, and Univeristy of Bologna).</p> <p>Moreover, a necessary extension will involve the integration of texts obtained through OCR and HTR processes conducted with tools such as EScriptorium and Transkribus. It was not possible to obtain texts through OCR and HTR processes within the scope of the current project, due to limited human resources.</p>	<p>As a demonstration of the DIACU dataset's potential, we implemented a machine-learning classifier to assign texts in (Old) Church Slavonic and Ruthenian to distinct chronological periods. The classifier was trained in a four-class setup, encompassing all temporal categories represented in the dataset. We selected logistic regression due to its proven efficiency and reliability in text classification tasks. Importantly, this experiment serves primarily to validate the dataset rather than to function as a definitive tool for the temporal attribution of texts in (Old) Church Slavonic and Ruthenian.</p> <p>Building further on the DIACU dataset, we are also developing a tool to classify individual words according to the regional variants of the texts in which they appear. This approach is intended to facilitate the study of dialectal and regional linguistic variation, enabling computational analyses of texts across both time and space.</p>
Church Slavonic	Retrieval Tool in the Marketplace	DaMSym Church Slavonic	<p>The semantic retrieval tool for Slavonic operates using the multilingual Jina model, the same model employed for Arabic, and is based on the BERT model architecture. This semantic retrieval tool is built upon the DIACU dataset, which was specifically created to support its development.</p> <p>The primary objective, as in other case studies, is to retrieve semantically related sentences, using the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed as a case study. However, the tool is also capable of processing sentences drawn from other texts. Compared to the versions developed for the other case studies, this iteration of the tool incorporates a filter that allows the distinction of language according to different historical periods of Slavonic, as well as Ruthenian, and a filter to identify the various historical and regional variants of the language.</p> <p>Additionally, we have implemented a font-selection filter to ensure the correct rendering of input queries, thereby addressing issues related to the use of non-Unicode characters. The font field has been designed to be continuously updatable, allowing it to reflect in real time any expansion of the dataset.</p>	https://uat-damsym-itserr.d4science.org/slavonic	https://uat-damsym-itserr.d4science.org/slavonic	<p>The integration of the tool into the ITSERR marketplace will necessarily need to be accompanied by a comprehensive user guide, providing all the information required for its effective use. Additionally, tests are currently underway to evaluate potential integrations or modifications aimed at improving both the presentation and the functionality of the tool.</p> <p>Its performance is expected to improve significantly once the dataset on which it operates is expanded to include texts generated through OCR and HTR processes, rather than relying solely on texts retrieved from online digital libraries.</p> <p>A key future development will be the training of a model capable of working with texts in (Old) Church Slavonic, which has not been feasible thus far due to the limited availability of texts.</p>	<p>The tool has been tested by some members of the scholar community specializing in Slavic philology, digital humanities, and the history of Orthodox Slavic countries. The tool's description, an analysis of its results when applied to the Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed, as well as the opinions and revisions provided by the scholar community to whom a test on the results obtained using the tool was submitted, have been analyzed in a co-authored article, which is currently under peer review.</p>

Church Slavonic	Dataset (es. corpus)	Dataset of relevant religious terms - the Nicene Costantinopolitan Creed	<p>The present dataset is still under development; however, it is mentioned in this form because it will constitute one of the outcomes of the research conducted within the project devoted to the study of Old Church Slavonic.</p>	The link is not yet available.	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1D3U1P5gPhtv5PUYpwXoo5Di41YZgAhS3	<p>The dataset will be used as a gold standard to refine the developed semantic analysis tool and may also serve as a starting point for the development of a model specifically tailored to Old Church Slavonic; it is intended to be expanded in future work.</p>
Church Slavonic	Software (e.g. lemmatizer)	OCSLemmatizer&ConverterCombined	<p>The present tool was developed in response to the limitations that led to the creation of a Unicode character converter and a lemmatizer for texts in Old Church Slavonic and Church Slavonic. The aim is to integrate the functionalities of both tools into a single application, thereby simplifying usability for future users. For this reason, the development of the three tools is currently proceeding in parallel; however, the long-term goal is to maintain and further develop this combined tool.</p>	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xUAEjz7lahV_iEYMV0p5KQjmhP39f1Oc?hl=it	<p>At present, this tool has not been developed for publication on the marketplace. For this reason, no operative web-link is currently available, and use of the tool requires following a dedicated installation procedure.</p>	